

Living with Wilson Disease in India:

Clinical Patterns, Patient Experiences, and Systemic Barriers

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Abstract

Wilson Disease (WD) is a rare autosomal recessive disorder that causes excessive copper accumulation in the body, particularly in the liver, brain, and other vital organs. This occurs due to a mutation in the ATP7B gene, which impairs the body's ability to eliminate excess copper. If untreated, Wilson disease can lead to severe liver and neurological damage, but with early diagnosis and proper management, individuals can lead normal lives. Although treatable, patients face diagnostic delays, limited drug access, and high psychosocial and financial burden. A survey of 47 WD patients in India documented clinical features and lived experiences. The median age of diagnosis was 11 years, presenting with hepatic, neurological, or psychiatric symptoms, consistent with national data. Diagnostic delays of 3 months up to 2 years were associated with misdiagnoses such as hepatitis or psychological disorders. Treatment primarily involved penicillamine, with intolerance and supply issues prompting use of Trientine and zinc salts in some cases. Patients faced significant socioeconomic burdens, including annual out-of-pocket costs of ₹1-3 lakh (USD 1100-3400), long travel distances, and missed schooling. Psychosocial challenges including stigma and social isolation were prevalent, though family support offered some resilience. The findings highlight systemic gaps in early diagnosis, affordable medication access, and comprehensive care for WD patients in India. Addressing these issues through policy reforms and their publicity, better drug availability, and specialized centres is crucial to improving patient outcomes.

Methods

Study Design

A prospective, observational, cross-sectional study over a period of six months (January-June 2025) was conducted on patients in India with established Wilson Disease (WD). The study

was carried out via telephonic interviews, filled questionnaires from respondents and physical interviews in consultation with physicians on the premises of the Department of Pediatric Gastroenterology at Sanjay Gandhi Postgraduate Institute of Medical Sciences (SGPGI), Lucknow, India.

Data Collection Tool

Patient information was collected using a preformed structured questionnaire designed in consultation with treating clinicians at SGPGI. The questionnaire covered six domains:

1. **Demographics** (age, sex, residence, family history, socioeconomic background).
2. **Clinical history** (age of symptom onset, type of presentation, progression).
3. **Diagnosis pathway** (time from symptoms to diagnosis, misdiagnoses, referral centres).
4. **Treatment history** (current and prior medications, drug availability, adverse reactions, costs, and source of medication procurement).
5. **Healthcare access and costs** (distance to tertiary care, frequency of follow-up, local provider awareness).
6. **Psychosocial impact** (schooling, employment, stigma, mental health, family/community support).

The questionnaire was filled either through face to face interviews or administered online (via Telephone/ WhatsApp), with clarifications and follow-up phone calls where necessary.

Patients

The study comprised a total of 47 patients with confirmed WD. Patients were recruited from multiple Indian states, including Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Rajasthan, Maharashtra, Gujarat and Delhi. They were primarily recruited either through the hospital outpatient department or through self-help communities created by Wilson Disease patients and their caregivers (in the form of WhatsApp and Facebook groups) seeking to source information or advise on Trientine (especially when it was not manufactured in India) Inclusion criteria were:

1. Confirmed diagnosis of WD established through Kayser-Fleischer (KF) rings, neurological symptoms, serum ceruloplasmin, liver and urinary copper values, and genetic analysis when available.
2. Age ≥ 8 years (able to self-report) or parent/guardian reporting for younger patients.
3. Willingness to provide informed consent (and assent in adolescents).

Consent and Ethics

Informed consent was obtained from adult participants and guardians of minors. Assent was also obtained from adolescents aged 12-17 years. All responses were anonymized before analysis to protect confidentiality. Patients were excluded if they had incomplete questionnaire data on key subjects.

Results

1. Demographics

The mean age of the survey respondents was 16 years, with a range from 8 to 32 years. The gender distribution was predominantly male, with approximately 83% male (n=39) and 17% female (n=8) respondents who self-identified their gender (Figure 1). No affected siblings were reported within the cohort; however, at least two cases mentioned early deaths of siblings due to unknown causes. The genetic history of WD in the family or known cases were also not reported.

Figure 1: Survey demographics: male (n=39) and female (n=8)

2. Clinical Presentation

The age at onset of symptoms ranged from 7 to 16 years, with a median age of 11 years. The presenting features included primarily hepatic symptoms in 85% (n=40) cases, such as jaundice, ascites, hepatomegaly, and vomiting. Neurological symptoms were observed in 4% (n=2) cases, manifesting as speech slurring, handwriting deterioration, and motor impairment, with both cases also exhibiting behavioural or learning issues. Additionally, 11% (n=5) cases

showed a combination of hepatic and neurological symptoms, including hepatomegaly along with seizures, drooling, and trembling. This distribution lies within the varied range quoted from different studies of the Indian cohort reported by Bhattacharya et al in 2022 (Bhattacharya et al in 2022) , which noted 0 to 100% in hepatic presentations and neuropsychiatric symptoms in different studies.

3. Diagnosis

The typical delay in diagnosis ranged from 3 to 12 months, with one case reporting a delay of almost two years. Many patients were initially misdiagnosed or undiagnosed by paediatricians, local doctors, or general physicians, often as hepatitis or jaundice, and in a few cases, as psychological or psychiatric conditions. Patients were subsequently referred to tertiary centres and specialists such as SGPGI, AIIMS, and KEM. There is no record that could be noted for comparison from earlier studies that cite the time gap between expression of symptom and a confirmed WD diagnosis.

In this cohort, 68% (n=32) of patients reported that their local physicians or paediatricians were unable to identify Wilson Disease at the initial stage, while 19% (n=9) were misdiagnosed and treated for unrelated conditions, most commonly hepatitis or psychiatric disorders. Only 13% (n=6) of respondents reported receiving a correct diagnosis of WD in the initial stage, underscoring a significant gap in clinical awareness and early detection of Wilson Disease (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Diagnostic Challenges in Wilson Disease. Correct Diagnosis (n=6), Misdiagnosis (n=9), Late Diagnosis (n=5), Unable to Diagnose (n=32)

4. Treatment History

Penicillamine was the first-line treatment; however, 17% of cases (n=8) within the cohort experienced intolerance characterized by rash, tremors, and worsening symptoms. Trientine was used as an alternative in the cases of intolerance. Although initially unavailable, it was later domestically produced but remained costly as an option. Zinc salts were used as adjunct therapy in some cases, with minor side effects such as nausea and anxiety. This treatment pattern aligns with Indian data reported by Kumar et al (Kumar et al in 2022), which also indicated penicillamine as the primary treatment with an intolerance rate of 25%, and Trientine being used as an alternative in 14% of the cases.

Figure 3: Allergic/Adverse Responses to Wilson Disease Medication: Penicillamine Allergy (n=9), Side Effects to Zinconia (n=2), No Allergic Responses (n=36)

5. Healthcare Access & Costs

Travel distances for patients ranged from 30 to 550 km, with a mean of 350 km. The annual treatment costs varied between ₹1 lakh and ₹3 lakh (approximately \$1100 to \$3400). Most patients had no insurance coverage, although 36% (n=17) received partial or full government aid. These findings are consistent with national data, which highlights the significant out-of-pocket expenses faced by patients, classified as catastrophic expenditure according to the World Health Organization in SDG Indicator 3.8.2 (“Catastrophic out-of-pocket health spending”, WHO).

CHALLENGES FACED BY WD PATIENTS IN ACCESSING MEDICATION

Figure 4: Challenges in Accessing Medication for Wilson Disease

Poor availability (n=12) is mostly seen in the case of Penicillamine in rural/ semi urban areas, Readily available medication (n=22) is mostly reflective of urban or bigger cities where Penicillamine is available overcoming the issues of availability during Covid, High cost but covered through partial or complete government aid (n=7) is seen in cases which are on Trientine medication and the cohort of feeling the pinch of high cost (n=4) are those patients who are on Trientine but not availing of government aid either due to ongoing treatment in private sector or lack of awareness of government schemes under NPRD 2022. Two cases did not comment on the challenges faced in accessing medication.

ARE LOCAL HEALTHCARE FACILITIES EQUIPPED TO TREAT WILSON DISEASE?

Figure 5: Are Local Healthcare Facilities Equipped to Treat Wilson Disease

A majority (n=39) reported lack of Healthcare facilities to treat WD. The cohort living in bigger cities had access (n=8) to the required facilities for treatment of WD.

6. Psychosocial Impact

77% of patients (n=37) reported interruptions in attending school, ranging from three months to two years. In older patients, the condition impacted employment in 4% patients (n=2), with limitations on roles that were physically less demanding or required minimal oral communication due to speech slurring. 17% patients (n=8) reported no disruption in their social, education or professional life. Stigma associated with the condition was reported but was less prominent than expected. Family support was universal among patients and served as a protective factor.

Figure 6: Responses to the social impact of Wilson Disease

Discussion

This study highlights the difficulties faced by patients with Wilson Disease (WD) in India, from diagnosis to treatment and day-to-day life. Although the number of patients in our study was small, the patterns observed corroborate the findings reported in larger Indian cohorts (Bhattacharya K. et al 2022, Nagral A et al 2019, Sanjay Kumar et al 2022, Ranjini Srinivasan et al 2024, Chakrapani Balijepalli et al 2021).

Clinical Presentation and Diagnosis

All patients in our cohort were diagnosed during late childhood or early adolescence, with ages at diagnosis ranging from 7 to 14 years, consistent with other Indian studies indicating that Wilson disease (WD) typically manifests between 8 and 15 years of age. Initial clinical

presentations predominantly involved hepatic symptoms such as jaundice, abdominal swelling, and recurrent vomiting, although many patients also exhibited neurological issues including speech, writing, or movement problems, as well as learning difficulties. In some cases, patients were initially misdiagnosed with psychological or behavioural disorders prior to establishing the correct diagnosis. A significant challenge observed was the delay in diagnosis, often extending from several months to over a year after symptom onset, primarily due to limited awareness and familiarity with WD among local healthcare providers, who frequently treated patients for more common conditions such as hepatitis. Most diagnoses were ultimately confirmed only after referral to specialized, resource-rich centres such as SGPGI, AIIMS, or KEM Hospital. These findings underscore the critical need for targeted training of healthcare professionals at primary and secondary medical facilities to improve early recognition and diagnosis of WD.

Treatment Challenges and Adverse Reactions

This cohort's therapeutic management aligns with established Indian practices for WD. Penicillamine remains the first-line treatment, however, intolerance is a common challenge, with patients reporting adverse effects such as allergic rashes, tremors, and symptom exacerbation. Consistent with published data from Indian cohorts, which report 25% intolerance rates and 14% in whom Trientine was used [Kumar et al, 2022], and Paradoxical Neurological Worsening (PNW) in 30-33% cases [Bhattacharya et al, 2022], our group of 47 patients demonstrated an intolerance rate of 17% (n=8). Trientine, used as an alternative, was generally better tolerated but faced significant barriers related to cost and availability. Although domestic manufacturing has improved access, the monthly expenses – approximately ₹12,000-24,000 – remain prohibitive for many, often resulting in treatment discontinuation. This situation reflects global advocacy findings, including WHO reports that emphasize disparities in access to essential medications. Zinc salts were employed in a few cases, typically well tolerated aside from occasional nausea or anxiety, serving as a temporary substitute for Penicillamine in one case and as a brief adjunct to Trientine in another. These observations underscore the dual challenges of drug intolerance and financial constraints, which are critical given WD's lifelong treatment requirements. Ensuring consistent, affordable access to both Penicillamine and Trientine is vital, and policy interventions such as price regulation, improved availability, and the inclusion of WD in the national rare disease policy with associated benefits are urgently warranted.

Impact on Daily Life and Families

WD had a significant impact on education, with most school-going patients (37 patients) missing several months to even years of classes, leading to academic setbacks and loss of social contact with peers. For adult patients, the primary challenges involved limited employment opportunities and social stigma. Families bore a substantial burden; parents of younger children reported high levels of stress, worry, and considerable disruption to their daily routines. Families of adult patients were also affected, though to a lesser degree, as the patients themselves were able to assume greater responsibility for their care. Interestingly, many families noted that over time, they developed better coping strategies, and managing daily life with the illness became somewhat easier.

Future Directions

The findings here suggest that there is a critical need to establish a comprehensive national registry for WD in India to systematically collect and monitor patient data, including clinical features, demographics, and treatment outcomes. Enhancing training programs for healthcare providers at both urban hospitals and rural health centres will facilitate earlier recognition of symptoms and timely diagnosis. Equally important is the development of support groups and peer networks, which can help reduce the social isolation experienced by many patients and their families. From a policy perspective, this survey indicates that although some patients benefit from government assistance in accessing medications, awareness of these programs remains limited. Increased advocacy and dissemination are necessary to promote the inclusion of WD in the National Policy for Rare Diseases, ensuring that patients requiring costly treatments like Trientine can access available aid through the NPRD 2021. Additionally, establishing state-level Centres of Excellence integrating neurology, hepatology, psychiatry, and social services would create a more holistic and accessible care infrastructure for individuals living with WD.

This approach provides a patient-centred approach, integrating both clinical data and lived experiences to inform the challenges associated with WD in India. The findings herein emphasize education, family burden, and mental health alongside clinical parameters.

The findings here are largely consistent with studies on Indian patients with WD (Bhattacharya K. et al 2022, Nagral A et al 2019, Sanjay Kumar et al 2022, Ranjini Srinivasan et al 2024, Chakrapani Balijepalli et al 2021). A number of common themes emerge including the manifestation of WD during childhood or adolescence but diagnosis is often delayed due to

early symptoms being misattributed to other conditions. In India, treatment primarily relies on Penicillamine, but many patients experience intolerance to the drug, while Trientine – despite being better tolerated – remains largely unaffordable for most families. Access to specialized care presents another significant obstacle, as many patients must travel considerable distances to consult experts. In addition to these medical challenges, WD frequently disrupts education, career trajectories, and social interactions, especially among young individuals. The convergence of medical, financial, and social burdens underscores the critical need for more accessible healthcare services and robust support systems for patients and their families.

Limitations

This study surveyed a small number of WD patients (n=47) with reliance on self-reported data thus making it difficult to rule out potential recall bias. The sample population was skewed towards urban and families connected to online resources. The findings of most marginalized rural populations remain to be investigated.

This 47-patient study demonstrates that clinical, diagnostic, and therapeutic patterns align with published Indian WD cohorts. The findings reinforce systemic gaps, delayed diagnosis, drug access/cost barriers, and inadequate psychosocial support, while adding patient-centered evidence of educational disruption and resilience.

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Author contributions

ZFB designed the survey, collected and analysed the data and wrote the manuscript.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

Use of AI

AI was used for editing the text.

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